

GENDER ANALYSIS ON KNOWLEDGE REGRADING MULBERRY CULTIVATION PRACTICES

G.R.Shivananada Gowda¹, M.T.Lakshminarayan² and Preethi³¹ Ph.D Scholar, Department of Agricultural Extension, University of Agricultural Sciences, Bangalore (UASB), Karnataka, India² Associate Professor (Agricultural Extension), University Examination Centre, UASB, Karnataka, India³ Scientist (Agricultural Extension), ICAR- Krishi Vignana Kendra, Babbur Farm, Hiriyur, Chitradurga, Karnataka, India
preethiuaahs@gmail.com

(MS Received: 17.05.2023; MS Revised:21.06.2023; MS Accepted:22.06.2023)

MS 3049

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL EXTENSION,)

Abstract

The present study was conducted during 2021-22 in two taluks of Ramanagara district in Karnataka state to assess the knowledge level of sericulture households regarding mulberry cultivation practices. Sixty farm men and women were interviewed using a pre-tested schedule. The results revealed that a large number of farm men had high level of knowledge (48.33%) on mulberry cultivation practices followed by 31.67 per cent and 20.00 per cent of farm men having medium and low level of knowledge on mulberry cultivation practices, respectively. On the contrary, a greater number of farm women were having medium level of knowledge (45.00%) regarding the mulberry cultivation practices, followed by 30.00 per cent and one-fourth of the farm women (25.00%) having low and high level of knowledge regarding the mulberry cultivation practices, respectively. The results also revealed that the 't' value (1.77) was found to be significant at five per cent level indicating that there exists a significant difference in the mean knowledge score between the farm men (26.33) and women (21.63) in respect of the mulberry cultivation practices.

Key words: Knowledge, Farm men, Farm women, Mulberry

Introduction

India is the second-largest producer of raw silk in the world and it has produced 34900 MT of raw silk during the year 2020-21. India was the world's largest consumer of raw silk as well as it is a greatest importer. Majority of the country's silk is produced in Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Assam, Bodoland, West Bengal, Jharkhand, and Tamil Nadu. In all these states, mulberry sericulture is primarily practised by the people. Sericulture is a big industry that spans a variety of agricultural, artistic, and technological fields, as well as textiles. It is valued as an agricultural industry by rural and resource-constrained farmers who cultivate mulberry and rear silkworms, but it is also viewed as a financial venture by other stakeholders. Since sericulture is a multipurpose agro-based industrial sector that serves all types of people worldwide, it appears to provide answers to the majority of concerns when most farmers have limited production resources, such as land and funds to spend on agriculture.

Sericulture is a high-yielding and highly profitable enterprise which offers regular and all-year-round attractive returns in the country's tropical states. Sericultural operations are typically limited to small or medium scale due to labour-intensive nature and individualised care is required for silkworm rearing operations, with most of the mulberry holdings in India ranging from 0.5 acres to 2 acres. Large-scale or commercial farming is now economically viable and popular, particularly among progressive farmers and educated people. Knowledge on improved cultivation technologies is a per-requisite for making decisions by the sericultural households for the adoption of the same in the field. Hence, the present study was undertaken with the following specific objectives:

To assess the knowledge level of farm men and women regarding mulberry cultivation practices

To find out the association between the profile characteristics of farm men and women with their knowledge level regarding mulberry cultivation practices

Methodology

The study was conducted in Ramanagara district of Karnataka State. Ramanagara is a well known as 'Silk City' and Sericulture is one of the main occupation in the district. In Karnataka, Ramanagara district stands third position in the cocoon production in terms of mulberry area (18,975 ha), cocoon production (19,662 tons) and cocoon productivity (89 kg/100 dfls) during 2020-21 next to Chikkaballapura and Kolar districts (Anonymous 2021a). During the year 2020-21, mulberry was grown in 9528, 3609, 2691 and 311 ha of Kanakapura, Channapatna, Ramanagara and Magadi taluks of Ramanagara district, respectively. The study was purposively conducted in Kanakapura (9525 ha) and Channapatna (3609 ha) taluks, since mulberry was grown in more areas among the four taluks of Ramanagara district (Anonymous, 2021b). Five villages were randomly selected for the study from each of the two sampled taluks. From each village, six farm households rearing silkworms were randomly selected. Relevant data were collected from the head of the family and his spouse. Thus, the final sample constituted 120 respondents (60 farm men and 60 farm women) from ten villages of Kanakapura and Channapatna taluks of Ramanagara district. Expost-facto research design was adopted for conducting the present study. Knowledge level of farm men and farm women operationalized in the present study as 'the quantum of scientific information known to the respondents about the recommended mulberry cultivation practices'. A total of 32 recommended mulberry cultivation practices were included to know the knowledge level of farm men and women. To assess the knowledge level of farm men and women, the respondents were given a score of 0 and 1 for having 'in correct knowledge and 'correct knowledge', respectively on each of the sericulture technologies. Thus, a minimum and maximum score one can get was 0 and 31, respectively. Based on the total score obtained for the 31 mulberry cultivation practices, the respondents were classified as low, medium and high level of knowledge using mean and half standard deviation as a measure of check.

Category	Criteria	Farm men	Farm women
Low	< (Mean - ½ SD)	<24.21	<19.98
Medium	(Mean ± ½SD)	24.21 to 28.45	19.98 to 23.28
High	> (Mean + ½ SD)	> 28.45	> 23.28
	Mean	26.33	21.63
	Standard deviation	4.24	3.31

The collected data was scored, tabulated and analysed using frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation and student 't' test.

Results and Discussion**Knowledge of farm men and women regarding recommended mulberry cultivation practices**

Knowledge on soil testing, land preparation and planting practices by farm men and women

It is observed from Table 1 that, a vast majority of farm men had correct knowledge on soil testing (2-3 years once) (96.66%) and soil type (red soil /sandy loam soil/laterite soil/red loamy soil) (93.33%), whereas a majority of farm women had correct knowledge on soil testing (2-3 years once) (60.00%) and soil type (red soil /sandy loam soil/laterite soil/red loamy soil) (61.66%). In respect of land preparation, an overwhelming number of the farm men possessed correct knowledge on deep digging (30-35 cm depth) /ploughing of land (90.00%) and pit size (1×1×1ft) (91.66%), whereas less than half of the farm women possessed correct knowledge on deep digging (30-35 cm depth) /ploughing of land (46.66%) and pit size (1×1×1ft) (38.34%).

With regard to spacing, it is observed from Table 1 that a majority of farm men had correct knowledge on the spacing provided for paired row system {(3×2ft)+5ft} (61.66%) and pit system (90×90cm) (88.34%), while a little over one-fourth of the farm men (26.66%) had correct knowledge on the spacing provided for the tree system (6×6,8×8,10×10 ft). On the other hand, a lesser number of farm women had correct knowledge on the spacing provided for paired row system {(3×2ft) +5ft} (26.66%) and pit system (90×90cm) (25.00%) and tree system (6×6,8×8,10×10 ft) (15.00 %).

Similarly, the results in Table 1 also reveals that a majority of the farm men had correct knowledge on the pit method (61.66%) and

paired row (88.34%) method of planting mulberry cuttings, while 26.66 per cent of the farm men had correct knowledge on the tree type of planting. Less than one-third of the farm women had correct knowledge on pit (26.66%), paired row (25.00%) and tree (15.00%) type of planting mulberry cuttings. Mulberry could be planted in all the three types of planting methods, however the pit system of planting is more popular in Ramanagar district compared to paired row and tree system of planting mulberry cuttings, hence less number of farm men and women possessed correct knowledge on tree system of planting mulberry cuttings.

Almost all the farm men had correct knowledge on the recommended variety of mulberry (V-1 and S36) (98.33%), while a majority of the farm women had correct knowledge on the recommended variety of mulberry (V-1 and S36) (68.33%). In respect of the preparation of mulberry cuttings, a vast majority of the farm men had correct knowledge on mulberry cuttings length (20-22 cm) (95.00%) and age of mulberry saplings to be planted in the main field (4 months old) (86.66%), whereas a majority of the farm women had correct knowledge on mulberry cuttings length (20-22 cm) (60.00%) and age of mulberry saplings to be planted in the main field (4 months old) (53.33%).

Table 1: Knowledge on soil testing, land preparation and planting practices by farm men and women

Sl. No.	Soil testing, land preparation and planting practices	Correct knowledge			
		Farm men (n ₁ =60)		Farm women (n ₂ =60)	
		No.	%	No.	%
1	Soil testing (2-3 years once)	58	96.66	36	60.00
2	Soil type (red soil /sandy loam soil/laterite soil/red loamy soil)	56	93.33	37	61.66
3.	Land preparation				
a	Deep digging (30-35 cm depth) /ploughing of land	54	90.00	28	46.66
b	Pit size (1×1×1ft)	55	91.66	23	38.34
c	Spacing				
i	Paired row system {(3×2)+5ft}	37	61.66	16	26.66
ii	Pit system (90×90cm)	53	88.34	15	25.00
iii	Tree system (6×6,8×8,10×10 ft)	16	26.66	09	15.00
d	Planting method				
i	Pit	37	61.66	16	26.66
ii	Paired row	53	88.34	15	25.00
iii	Tree type	16	26.66	09	15.00
4.	Mulberry variety (V-1/S36)	59	98.33	41	68.33
5	Preparation of mulberry cuttings				
a	Mulberry cuttings length (20-22 cm)	57	95.00	36	60.00
b	Age of mulberry saplings to be planted in the main field (4 months old)	52	86.66	32	53.33

Knowledge on manures, irrigation and weeding practices by farm men and women

A majority of the farm men possessed correct knowledge on the quantity of FYM/compost (20t/ha) (95.00%), quantity of fertilizers (350N:140P:140K/kg/ha) (93.33%) and quantity of micronutrients (2.5 litres of Seriboost/ha or 2.5 litre of poshan in 350 litres of water /ha) (71.66%) to be applied for mulberry crop, where a majority of the farm women possessed correct knowledge on quantity of FYM/compost (20t/ha) (53.33%) and quantity of fertilizers (350N:140P:140K/kg/ha) (61.66%) to be applied for mulberry crop (Table 2) . A little over one-third of the farm women (38.33%) possessed correct knowledge on the quantity of micronutrients (2.5 litres of Seriboost/ha or 2.5 litre of poshan in 350 litres of water /ha) to the mulberry crop.

In respect of the number of irrigations for mulberry crop, a greater majority of farm men had possessed correct knowledge on surface irrigation (2-3times/week) (86.66%), flood irrigation (2-3 times/week) (95.00%) and drip irrigation (45 time /week) (91.66%). Whereas, more than half of the farm women had correct knowledge on flood irrigation (2-3 times/week) (56.66%) and less than half of the farm women had correct knowledge on surface irrigation (2-3 times/week) (36.66%) and drip irrigation (45 time /week) (46.66%). It was noticed during the data collection the mulberry crop is being irrigated by all the three methods of irrigations by the respondents (Table 2).

With regard to the weeding in mulberry plots, a greater majority of the farm men possessed correct knowledge on number of weedings (15 days once) (96.66%) and application of weedicide (600 l/ha) (98.33%) (Table 2) , while a majority of the farm women had correct

knowledge on number of weedings (15 days once) (56.66%) and 45.00 per cent of the farm women possessed correct knowledge on application of weedicide (600 l/ha).

Table 2: Knowledge on manure, irrigation and weeding practices by farm men and women

Sl. No.	Manure, irrigation and weeding practices	Correct knowledge			
		Farm men (n ₁ =60)		Farm women (n ₂ =60)	
		No.	%	No.	%
1	Manures including micro nutrients				
a	Quantity of FYM/compost (20t/ha)	57	95.00	32	53.33
b.	Quantity of fertilizers (350N:140P:140K/kg/ha)	56	93.33	37	61.66
c	Quantity of micronutrients (2.5 litres of Seriboost/ha or 2.5 litre of poshan in 350 litres of water /ha)	43	71.66	23	38.33
2.	Number of irrigations				
a	Surface irrigation (2-3times/week)	52	86.66	22	36.66
b	Flood irrigation (2-3 times/week)	57	95.00	34	56.66
c	Drip irrigation (1.5-2 litre/day/plant)	55	91.66	28	46.66
3.	Weeding (once after 20 days of Pruning)				
a	Number of weedings (15 days once)	58	96.66	34	56.66
b	Application of weedicide (600l/ha)	59	98.33	27	45.00

Knowledge on integrated pest management and harvesting practices by farm men and women

With respect to the physical method of controlling pests, as high as 96.66 per cent of the farm men had correct knowledge on the installation of light traps /pheromone traps to attract defoliating pests in mulberry gardens, while 61.66 per cent of the farm women had correct knowledge on the installation of light traps /pheromone traps to attract defoliating pests in mulberry gardens (Table 3).

In respect of the chemical method of controlling pests, an overwhelming number of farm men possessed correct knowledge on spraying of 0.4% neem oil for managing pink mealy bug (93.33%), application of paste 0.1% malathion for managing stem borer (91.66%), spraying of 0.2% carbendazim mixed with 50% WP (wetttable power) to manage leaf spot disease (96.66%), spraying of 0.2% carbendazim with 50% WP (wetttable power) to control powdery mildew (98.33%), spraying of 100ppm (parts per million) streptomycin @1g/10L to manage blast disease (96.66%) and spraying of 0.1% of carbendazim to manage stem canker disease (93.33%), whereas less than half of the farm women possessed correct knowledge on spraying of 0.4% neem oil for managing pink mealy bug (43.33%), application of paste 0.1% malathion for managing stem borer (41.66%), spraying of 0.2% carbendazim

mixed with 50% WP (wetttable power) to manage leaf spot disease (35.00%), spraying of 0.2% carbendazim with 50% WP(wetttable power) @48EC to control powdery mildew (41.66%), spraying of 100 ppm (parts per million) streptomycin @1g/10L to manage blast disease (40.00%) and spraying of 0.1% of carbendazim to manage stem canker disease (33.33%) (Table 3).

The results pertaining to the biological method of controlling pests, it was found that a vast majority of the farm men had correct knowledge on releasing of egg parasitoid @ 10 tricho cards/ha to control of leaf webber (91.66%), while a little over one-third of the farm women had correct knowledge on releasing of egg parasitoid @ 10 tricho cards/ha to leaf webber (35.00% (Table 3).

In respect of harvesting of mulberry leaves, the results in Table 3 also revealed that all the farm men had correct knowledge on time of harvesting (morning/evening) (100.00%), while a vast majority of them (98.33%) had correct knowledge regarding the period of harvesting of leaves (30 days from DAP (day of pruning)/ 35days from DAP/40days from DAP/45days from DAP). On the other hand, almost all the farm women had correct knowledge on time of harvesting (morning/evening) (98.33%) and period of harvesting of leaves (30 days from DAP (day of pruning)/ 35days from DAP/40days from DAP/ 45days from DAP) (96.66%).

Table 3: Knowledge on integrated insect, disease and harvesting management practices by farm men and women

Sl. No.	Integrated pest management and harvesting practices	Correct knowledge			
		Farm men (n ₁ =60)		Farm women (n ₂ =60)	
		No.	%	No.	%
1	Integrated pest and disease management practices				
a	Physical method				
i	Installing light traps /pheromone traps to attract defoliating pests in mulberry garden	58	96.66	37	61.66
b.	Chemical method				
i	Spraying of 0.4% neem oil for managing pink mealy bug	56	93.33	26	43.33
ii	Application of paste 0.1% malathion for managing stem borer	55	91.66	25	41.66
iii	Spraying of 0.2% carbendazim mixed with 50% WP (wetttable power) to manage leaf spot disease	58	96.66	21	35.00
iv	Spraying of 0.2% carbendazim with 50% WP (wetttable power) to control powdery mildew	59	98.33	25	41.66

v	Spraying of 100 ppm (parts per million) streptocyclin @ 1g/10L to manage blast disease	58	96.66	24	40.00
vi	Spraying of 0.1% of carbendazim to manage stem canker disease	56	93.33	20	33.33
c	Biological method				
i	Releasing of egg parasitoid @ 10 tricho cards/ac to control of leaf webber	55	91.66	21	35.00
2	Harvesting practices				
a.	Time of harvesting (moming/evening)	60	100.00	59	98.33
b.	Period of harvesting of leaves (30days from DAP (day after pruning)/35days from DAP/40days from DAP/45days from DAP)	59	98.33	58	96.66

The results in Tables 1 to 3 revealed that almost all the farm men had correct knowledge regarding the recommended mulberry cultivation practices, while less than half of the farm women had correct knowledge on deep digging, pit size, spacing, planting method, quantity of micro nutrients applied for mulberry crop, irrigation, application of weedicide, and chemical and biological methods of controlling pests. Due to lack of awareness among the farm women regarding the above technologies, majority of the farm women did not possess correct knowledge on deep digging, pit size, spacing, planting method, quantity of micro nutrients applied for mulberry crop, irrigation, application of weedicide, chemical and biological methods of controlling pests. The above technologies involve more of physical work and farm women do not regularly perform these operations in the mulberry field, hence less than half of the farm women lack knowledge on these technologies.

Overall knowledge of farm men and women regarding the recommended mulberry cultivation practices.

Table 4: Overall knowledge of farm men and women regarding the mulberry cultivation practices

Sl. No.	Knowledge category	Number	Per cent	Standard deviation	Mean knowledge score	't' value
A	Farm men (n ₁ =60)					
1	Low (<24.21 score)	12	20.00	4.24	26.33	1.77*
2	Medium (24.21 to 28.45 score)	19	31.67			
3	High (>28.45 score)	29	48.33			
	Total	60	100.00			
B	Farm women (n ₂ =60)					
1	Low (<19.98 score)	18	30.00	3.31	21.63	
2	Medium (19.98 to 23.28 score)	27	45.00			
3	High (>23.28 score)	15	25.00			
	Total	60	100.00			

*Significant at 5%

Conclusion

The results revealed that a large number of farm men had high level of knowledge (48.33%) on recommended mulberry cultivation practices, while a greater number of farm women were having medium level of knowledge (45.00%) regarding the recommended cultivation practice. There existed a significant difference in the mean knowledge score between the farm men and women in respect of the recommended mulberry cultivation practices. There is a need to provide good opportunities for both farm men and women to participate in the sericulture extension and the media might also publish/broadcast/telecast on information/messages/programmes on the mulberry cultivation practices helping the sericulture households

It is observed from Table 4 that a large number of farm men had high level of knowledge (48.33%) on recommended mulberry cultivation practices followed by 31.67 per cent and 20.00 per cent of farm men having medium and low level of knowledge on recommended mulberry cultivation practices, respectively. On the contrary, a greater number of farm women were having medium level of knowledge (45.00%) regarding the recommended cultivation practices, followed by 30.00 per cent and one-fourth of the farm women (25.00%) having low and high level of knowledge regarding the recommended mulberry cultivation practices, respectively. The results also revealed that the 't' value (1.77) was found to be significant at five per cent level indicating that there exists a significant difference in the mean knowledge score between the farm men (26.33) and women (21.63) in respect of the recommended mulberry cultivation practices. The findings are in line with the findings reported by Vikas (2020).

to increase their knowledge leading to adoption of the same in the mulberry field for obtaining increased leaf yield and income

References

1. **Anonymous, 2021a**, Annual Report of Central Silk Board: <http://www.csb.gov.in/assets/uploads/documents/CSBAR1617English.pdf>.
2. **Anonymous, 2021b**, Annual Report, Department of Sericulture, Karnataka.
3. **Vikas, 2020**, A study on knowledge, yield gap and extent of adoption of recommended production technologies by maize growers in Koppal district. *M.Sc. (Agri) Thesis (Unpub.)*, Univ. Agric. Sci., Bangalore.